

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

9th International conference **CHEMICAL REACTIONS IN FOODS IX (CRF 2023)**

September 13-15, 2023

Prague, Czech Republic

Jana Pulkrabová, Monika Tomaniová, Marco Arlorio, Vincenzo Fogliano,
and Jana Hajšlová
Editors

P35**APPLICATION OF GREEN EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGIES IN FRUITS: INNOVATIONS WITHIN THE EXCEL4MED PROJECT**

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The overarching objective of EXCEL4MED is to create an Excellence Hub in Mediterranean fruit supply chains. The project aims at identifying high-impact strategies and establish lines of resilience for producers, processors, consumers and policymakers. Overall, EXCEL4MED will offer an adaptive capability in the Mediterranean supply chain preparing for novel waste valorisation strategies, production of added value fruit products following a holistic commerce, and the implementation of green innovative technological methodologies. EXCEL4MED will develop and demonstrate the solution in Mediterranean high-value perishable food supply chains: pomegranate and citrus fruits. EXCEL4MED will develop a conceptual design and pre-planning for pilots and demonstrators of electrochemical and sonochemical technologies in the food industry. For that purpose proof of concepts and scale-up validation assessments will be developed for the pomegranate and citrus food chains. This will be achieved by consolidating academic business linkages and providing evidence for strategy building and investment. Application of green processes for improved extraction of bioactive compounds from pomegranate seed oil, citrus and pomegranate pericarps will be carried out. Experimental studies are currently carried out to characterize the bioactive compounds of different pomegranate and citrus varieties. The effectiveness of Electric Field (PEF), Ultrasound (US) and Hydrodynamic Cavitation (HC) as pre-treatments are compared to standard methods e.g., using enzymes, as well as to hybrid treatments. The bioactive compounds are extracted using standard methods, following characterization and quantification. The antioxidant capacity of the bioactive substances are determined through the radical scavenging method (DPPH), the Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power Assay (FRAP) and the ABTS radical cation reduction test. The best-performed treatment conditions will be identified and selected. EXCEL4MED will create 4 pilot projects in Malta and Greece; 3 on added value products and 1 on valorisation. At the end of the project, partners will provide the pilot regions specific recommendations for a joint policy in food processing, taking into consideration already identified innovation strategies for smart specialization.

Keywords: extraction, green technologies, citrus, technology, sustainability

Acknowledgement: European Unions Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under GA No 101079173.